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A network of homeobox factors that specify CNS metastasis.

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We report here discovery of a network of homeobox transcription factors whose expression specifies metastasis to the central nervous system (CNS) in humans with breast cancer.

Results

We used RNA-sequencing (published) to measure total transcription in the brain metastasis of humans with CNS metastatic breast cancer, and in the primary tumor of the breast, to perform differential gene expression analysis and extract and identify the most distinguishing transcriptional features of metastasis to the CNS in humans with breast cancer.

%DE	Rank	GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Description
0.41%	87	3149	1.17E-10	0.4816	-6.442935	-3.10323033	2567.18	HMGB3	high mobility group box 3
								SOX11	SRY-box transcription factor 11
0.66%	142	3228	1.54E-09	0.891	-6.0398021	-5.38150379	152.73	HOXC12	homeobox C12
0.84%	180	10736	5.79E-09	0.6514	-5.8226408	-3.79260071	589.87	SIX2	SIX homeobox 2
3.57%	764	3607	6.44E-06	0.5069	-4.5113763	-2.28685902	3375.79	FO XK2	forkhead box K2
4.22%	904	286380	1.38E-05	0.4553	-4.3463252	-1.97877684	10.12	FOXD4L3	forkhead box D4 like 3
4.52%	968	5080	1.84E-05	0.5216	-4.2831881	-2.23421227	68.55	PAX6	paired box 6
5.19%	1111	5455	3.23E-05	0.9286	-4.1569228	-3.85995877	40.67	POU3F3	POU class 3 homeobox 3
5.81%	1244	3226	5.31E-05	0.6841	-4.0417209	-2.76495455	717.12	HOXC10	homeobox C10
6.12%	1310	2302	7.04E-05	0.8304	-3.974771	-3.30053253	290.56	FOXJ1	forkhead box J1
6.90%	1476	2298	1.13E-04	0.7359	-3.8597916	-2.84055708	112.48	FOXD4	forkhead box D4
7.00%	1498	3227	1.19E-04	0.8949	-3.8486553	-3.44412833	432.39	HOXC11	homeobox C11
8.09%	1731	3229	2.15E-04	0.7372	-3.7002138	-2.72781725	215.44	HOXC13	homeobox C13
8.36%	1789	1747	2.40E-04	0.6838	-3.6724727	-2.51124495	70.05	DLX3	distal-less homeobox 3
9.55%	2045	5075	4.16E-04	1.2615	-3.52952	-4.45248316	78.57	PAX1	paired box 1
9.76%	2088	5013	4.55E-04	0.7072	-3.5058261	-2.47926896	95.34	OTX1	orthodenticle homeobox 1
10.05%	2150	6495	5.22E-04	0.6465	-3.4691402	-2.24279654	823.09	SIX1	SIX homeobox 1
11.27%	2412	4825	8.43E-04	0.8432	-3.3382803	-2.81478075	20.54	NKX6-1	NK6 homeobox 1
11.89%	2545	3223	1.05E-03	0.7173	-3.2760786	-2.35003462	1042.4	HOXC6	homeobox C6
12.31%	2634	51804	1.20E-03	0.49	-3.2389179	-1.58717343	411.58	SIX4	SIX homeobox 4
13.73%	2938	653404	1.76E-03	0.5135	-3.1278304	-1.60602258	10.06	FOXD4L6	forkhead box D4 like 6
14.09%	3016	200350	1.92E-03	0.6277	-3.1026635	-1.94741802	18.04	FOXD4L1	forkhead box D4 like 1
14.55%	3115	5454	2.17E-03	0.98	-3.0654693	-3.00429303	12.97	POU3F2	POU class 3 homeobox 2

Figure 1: A network of homeobox factors that specify CNS metastasis.

The CNS metastatic homeobox network was most significantly enriched in expression of the high mobility group box *Hmgb3* (**Figure 1**). Multiple members of the Hox C family including homeobox C12 (HoxC12), homeobox C10 (HoxC10), homeobox C11 (HoxC11) and homeobox C13 (HoxC13) were activated and enriched in the CNS metastasis. Other members of the network included *Pou3f2* and *Pou3f3*, related to *Pou5f1* which functions in execution of pluripotency, as well as Six homeobox family members SIX2 and SIX4. Paired box 6 (PAX6) and paired box 1 (PAX1) were also members of the CNS metastasis homeobox network; we recently demonstrated a requirement for *PAX8* in transformation of human cells *in vitro* by oncogenic RasG12V, and unpublished data from our lab indicates a broader role for PAX8 and a non-coding (anti-sense) RNA produced from the PAX8 locus, *PAX8-AS1*, indicating importance of PAX family members in induction and maintenance of transformation, in the primary tumor and in metastasis *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

We studied total transcription following genetic depletion of a select number of the homeoboxes that exist as part of the CNS metastatic network (**Figure 2**). Depletion of SIX2 resulted in significant reduction in the major solid tumor transcript ECT2, demonstrating sufficiency and necessity of homeobox factors in maintenance of the transformed state. At the transcriptome level, depletion of SIX2 was similar to depletion of PAX8 in magnitude of ECT2 reduction, further suggesting that targeted inhibition of select homeoboxes represent attractive therapeutic strategies to treat primary and metastatic disease in humans with solid tumors (cancer).

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10736	0	0.0882	41.533195	3.662538	1159.05	SIX2	1/16896	99.99
1894	2.47e44	0.0549	13.967	0.767	2385.65	ECT2	56/16896	99.7

1 In a separate report, we describe induction of the SRY-box homeobox factor SOX11 in CNS
2 metastasis, whose expression, which defines the HER2+ subtype and specifies the CNS metastasis,
3 appears to reconcile (in part) the concept that the subtype itself is a determinant of high CNS metastasis
4 rate.

4 **Discussion**

5 Six years after we began using next generation technologies to study metastasis to the central
6 nervous system in humans with cancer, including in humans with HER2+ breast cancer, who experience
7 CNS metastasis at a remarkable 50% frequency, two years after our discovery of ECT2, a gene whose
8 magnitude and direction of expression distinguishes the solid tumor in humans and which will allow
9 unprecedented identification of cancer at the population level, and a year following our discovery of the
10 HER2+ CNS locus, a discrete region of the human genome which includes the *ERBB2* gene and whose
11 gene members in composite contribute to overall or distant-metastasis survival in humans with CNS
12 metastasis, we report identification of a network of homeobox factors whose expression specifies
13 metastasis to the CNS. The data are one part of a larger concept which suggest homeobox factors
14 function together, in a concentric or “reinforced” manner, to support maintenance of the transformed state
15 in humans with cancer.
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